

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part IX. Synthesis and Study of Some New 3-Methyl-5-aryl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) isoxazoles as Possible Antibacterials

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Eight series of 3-methyl-5-aryl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) isoxazoles have been synthesised by condensing hydroxylamine hydrochloride with the appropriate 2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) arylacetones. The antibacterial properties of these compounds are evaluated and some of these found to exhibit marked activity.

A number of isoxazole derivatives have been found to be potential antibacterials¹, antitubercular², antifungal³ and antiviral⁴ agents. Sulpha drugs containing the isoxazole nucleus are stable compounds and characterised by low toxicity and strong activity *in vivo* against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and in comparison to other sulpha drugs are non-irritant and do not accumulate in the kidney. 3,4-Dimethyl-5-sulphanilamido isoxazole⁵ (Gantrisin), a member of this class was found to be therapeutically active and is used as a drug even today.

Isoxazoles having the arylazo group attached at position-4 have been reported to possess antidiabetic⁶ and agricultural fungicidal activity⁷.

3,5-Diaryl-and 3-Methyl-5-aryl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo)pyrazoles have recently been reported to exhibit activity *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*⁸⁻¹⁰, and perusal of literature indicated that hardly any work has been carried out on the synthesis and study of the isoxazole derivatives having a sulphonamide moiety attached at position-4 through an azo-linkage. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to synthesize some 4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) isoxazoles and study their antibacterial properties *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. The present communication describes the synthesis of 3-methyl-5-aryl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) isoxazoles of the type I by the condensation of 1-(4'-chlorophenyl)-, 1-(4'-bromophenyl)-, 1-(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenyl)-, 1-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-, 1-(4'-ethoxyphenyl)-, 1-(4'-methylphenyl)-, 1-(4'-ethylphenyl)-, and 1-biphenyl-3-methyl-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The homogeneity and purity of these compounds was tested by T.L.C. and elemental analysis. The yields in all cases were fairly good and ranged from 60 to 85%.

Experimental

Different 1-aryl-3-methyl-2-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones required for this work were prepared by the method already described.^{1,11,12}

3-Methyl-5-aryl-4-(substituted sulphonamidobenzeneazo) isoxazoles 3-Methyl-5-(p-methylphenyl)-4-(sulphanylbenzeneazo) isoxazole

1-(*p*-Methylphenyl)-3-methyl-2-(sulphanylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-dione (0.1g) in glacial acetic acid (3 ml) was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.05g) in presence of sodium acetate and few drops of water in an oil bath at 170-180° for 7-8 hr. The red solid which separated out was filtered, dried and crystallised from alcohol-glacial acetic acid and had m.p. 201°. (Yield 0.07g; 73%).

(Found: C, 57.2; H, 4.8. C₁₇H₁₆O₃N₄S requires C, 57.3; H, 5.0%).

Other isoxazoles synthesised in the similar manner are entered in Tables 1 to 8.

TABLE 1—3-METHYL-5-(4'-CHLOROPHENYL)-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) ISOXAZOLES
(I : Ar=4-chlorophenyl)

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial <i>S. aureus</i>	activity <i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	230	O	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ SCl	(-)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	230	O	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₄ SCl	(+)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	220	R	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₄ SCl	(+)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	222	O	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ SCl	(-)	(-)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	205	O	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ SCl	(+)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	220	R	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ SCl	(+)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	289	OY	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₆ SCl	(+)	(-)
8.	α -Pyridyl	250	R	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
9.	Pyrimidyl	264	O	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₅ SCl	(+)	(-)
10.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	216	OY	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₆ SCl	(-)	(-)
11.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	240	O	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₆ SCl	(+)	(-)
12.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	220	R	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₆ SCl	(+)	(-)
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	269	O	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂ Cl	(+++)	(+)
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	233	O	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(-)

TABLE 2—3-METHYL-5-(4'-BROMOPHENYL)-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) ISOXAZOLES
(I ; Ar=4-bromophenyl)

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial <i>S. aureus</i>	activity <i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	232	OR	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ SBr	(-)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	232	OY	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₄ SBr	(-)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	214	O	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₄ SBr	(-)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	228	OR	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ SBr	(-)	(-)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	198	OY	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ SBr	(-)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	219	OR	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ SBr	(-)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	276	Y	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₆ SBr	(+)	(-)
8.	α -Pyridyl	252	O	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₅ SBr	(+)	(-)
9.	Pyrimidyl	263	O	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)
10.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	200	OR	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₆ SBr	(-)	(-)
11.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	252	OY	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₆ SBr	(+)	(-)
12.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	220	R	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₆ SBr	(+)	(-)
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	266	OR	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂ Br	(+++)	(-)
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	235	O	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₅ SBr	(-)	(+)

TABLE 3—3-METHYL-5-(4'-CHLORO-3'-METHYLPHENYL)-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) ISOXAZOLES
(I ; Ar=4-chloro-3-methylphenyl)

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial <i>S. aureus</i>	activity <i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	231	OY	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ SCl	(-)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	228	OY	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₄ SCl	(+)	(+)
3.	Phenyl	203	OY	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ SCl	(-)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	210	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₄ SCl	(-)	(-)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	193	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₄ SCl	(-)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	205	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₄ SCl	(-)	(+)
7.	Guanidyl	240	O	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₆ SCl	(+)	(-)
8.	α -Pyridyl	244	O	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(+)
9.	Pyrimidyl	256	O	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₅ SCl	(+)	(-)
10.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	227	O	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₆ SCl	(-)	(-)
11.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	217	YO	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₆ SCl	(+)	(+)
12.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	223	OY	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₆ SCl	(+)	(-)
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	264	O	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂ Cl	(+++)	(+)
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	230	O	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₅ SCl	(-)	(-)

TABLE 4—3-METHYL-5-(4'-METHOXYPHENYL)-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENAZO) ISOXAZOLES
 (I : Ar=4-methoxyphenyl)

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity <i>S. aureus</i>	activity <i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	220	O	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
2.	Phenyl	212	Y	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ S	(+)	(+)
3.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	219	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄ S	(+)	(+)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	185	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₄ S	(+)	(+)
5.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	214	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₄ S	(+)	(+)
6.	Guanidyl	288	YO	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
7.	α -Pyridyl	249	R	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₅ S	(+)	(-)
8.	Pyrimidyl	260	O	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
9.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	160	R	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
10.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	195	Y	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
11.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	224	Y	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
12.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	253	O	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	(+++)	(+)
13.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	222	O	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₅ S	(+)	(+)

 TABLE 5—3-METHYL-5-(4'-ETHOXYPHENYL)-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) ISOXAZOLES
 (I : Ar=4-ethoxyphenyl)

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity <i>S. aureus</i>	activity <i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	218	B	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ S	(-)	(+)
2.	Acetyl	220	Y	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄ S	(-)	(+)
3.	Phenyl	208	OY	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	200	Y	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	185	O	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	213	R	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	260	OR	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
8.	α -Pyridyl	225	R	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₅ S	(-)	(+)
9.	Pyrimidyl	244	R	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₆ S	(-)	(+)
10.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	168	R	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
11.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	225	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
12.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	225	R	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	243	Y	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	(+++)	(+)
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	218	Y	C ₂₅ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)

 TABLE 6—3-METHYL-5-(4'-METHYLPHENYL)-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) ISOXAZOLES
 (I : Ar=4-methylphenyl)

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity <i>S. aureus</i>	activity <i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	201	R	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ S	(+)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	206	OY	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ S	(+)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	200	R	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄ S	(+)	(+)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	200	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	196	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	221	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄ S	(+)	(+)
7.	Guanidyl	252	R	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
8.	α -Pyridyl	235	R	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₅ S	(+)	(-)
9.	Pyrimidyl	248	R	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
10.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	165	R	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₆ S	(-)	(+)
11.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	235	R	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
12.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	198	R	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	250	R	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(+++)	(+)
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	210	R	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₅ S	(+)	(+)

TABLE 7—3-METHYL-3-(4'-ETHYLPHENYL)-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) ISOXAZOLES

(I : Ar = 4-ethylphenyl)

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity <i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	220	RO	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₄ S	(-)	(+)
2.	Acetyl	219	OR	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ S	(+)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	212	RO	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₄ S	(-)	(+)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	217	O	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	(-)	(+)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	174	O	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₄ S	(-)	(+)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	207	O	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₄ S	(-)	(+)
7.	Guanidyl	245	Y	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S	(-)	(+)
8.	α -Pyridyl	230	O	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)
9.	Pyrimidyl	234	R	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
10.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	145	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
11.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	242	O	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
12.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	186	YO	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	(-)	(+)
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	240	O	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(++)	(+)
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	209	O	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)

TABLE 8—3-METHYL-5-BIPHENYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDOBENZENEAZO) ISOXAZOLES

(I : Ar = biphenyl)

S. No.	R	M. P. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity <i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	240	YO	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	225	Y	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ S	(+)	(+)
3.	Phenyl	225	R	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₄ S	(-)	(+)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	222	O	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	(-)	(+)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	210	R	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	213	OR	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	242	O	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
8.	α -Pyridyl	244	R	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₅ S	(+)	(-)
9.	Pyrimidyl	252	O	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
10.	4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	240	R	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
11.	2, 6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	228	Y	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
12.	2, 6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	241	OR	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
13.	5-Methyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl	244	O	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S ₂	(++)	(+)
14.	<i>n</i> -Butylcarbamido	239	Y	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₅ S	(-)	(-)

B = Brown ; O = Orange ; OY = Orange yellow ; OR = Orange red ; R = Red ; RO = Reddish orange ; Y = Yellow ; YO = Yellowish orange.

All the compounds gave satisfactory analysis for C and H

Antibacterial activity

All the isoxazole derivatives have been screened *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by the cup-plate agar diffusion method at two different concentrations, 500 μ g/ml and 1000 μ g/ml and the results with the dilutions of 500 μ g/ml have been entered in Tables 1-8.

The results indicate that though all these types of compounds show activity but the number of compounds

found active against *S. aureus* far exceeds those against *E. coli*. Another observation is that if the halogens attached to the aromatic ring at position-5 are replaced by an electron repelling group, such as, methoxyl, the activity against both the organisms is enhanced to a considerable extent and this is in confirmation of our earlier observations^{8,9}. Another point worth mentioning is that isoxazoles having the 5-methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl ring in the sulphonamide moiety are found to be the most active compounds against *S. aureus*.

References

1. T. OKUDA, J. KITAMURA and K. A. AZIKA, *Proc. Oifu. Coll. Pharm.*, 1955, **5**, 2083.
2. C. CARADONNA and M. L. STEIN, *Farmaco. Edn. Sci.*, 1960, **15**, 647.
3. K. S. R. KRISHNAMOHAN and N. V. SUBBA RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 66.
4. N. STELGER, U. S. PAT., 2,55,564,4 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1951, **45**, 10259.
5. E. N. PERSHIN, A. N. KOST, L. G. OVERSEVA and WEI. Pi-Ting, *Vestn., Mosk. Univ., Ser II., khim.*, 1963, **18**, 69 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, **58**, 4537f.
6. H. G. GARG and P. P. SINGH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 1250.
7. Imperial Chemical Industries Ltd. (Belg.), 617,389, Nov. 8, 1962, Brit. Appl. Nov. 2, 1960, and July 31, 1961.
8. G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 351.
9. G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, (in press).
10. C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA, and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 985.
11. C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Def. Sci. J.*, 1975, **25**, 55.
12. C. MOHAN, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *Def. Sci. J.*, 1975, **25**, 97.